

LEIDEN UNIVERSITY &
GOVERNMENT OF THE NETHERLANDS

PH.D. PROJECT

Problem Statement

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This document provides the problem statement for the proposed PhD project along with the associated research objectives and -questions.

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Document History

Version	Date	Author	Comment
1.0	12-03-2024	R. Kievit	First complete version of this document. Version was submitted to Prof.Dr. Mirjam van Reisen for first review.
1.1	18-03-2024	R. Kievit	Revised version after feedback by Prof.Dr. Mirjam van Reisen. Mostly shifted focus of synthesis and RQ/RO away from specifically personal data, and more towards the bigger picture.
1.2	19-03-2024	R. Kievit	Revised version after discussion with GAIC peer group (M. Basjja, P. Jati, K. Smits). Extended RQ and RO into five subs.

1 Introduction

Public administrations handle enormous volumes of data in order to fulfill their legal obligations. This data is often stored in many different silos that are unable to efficiently communicate with each other. Enabling re-use through data sharing and interoperability can greatly increase the efficiency of a government in performing its tasks. However, which information can be shared with whom should be carefully considered. Most of the data generated by a public administration can be made publicly available, however there are many cases where access should be restricted such as when personal privacy or national security play a role. Ideally, automated authentication and authorization mechanisms should be put in place to ensure safe, privacy-preserving communication of data.

The field of authorization has been the focus of many works since the 1950's. In recent decades, concepts of the Semantic Web have slowly been integrated in various implementations. The Semantic Web is a promising technology capable of enabling, among many other benefits, interoperability between (distributed) heterogeneous data sources largely through the use of rich semantic metadata.

No consensus yet exists regarding the design of a semantics-based, dynamic and distributed architecture for authorization. Some examples of current approaches are: a centralized mechanism which makes authorization decisions based on access policies, user- and data attributes, and potentially context variables (Arshad et al., 2022; Hilia et al., 2017; Kamateri et al., 2014; Khan et al., 2017; Bader et al., 2021); the exploitation of patterns in the linked data graphs stored on Solid Personal Data Stores (Werbrouck et al., 2020); an expansion of the SPARQL query language to protect guarded data by inferring the intent of a data request (Stojanov et al., 2018); and an automatic agent-based model that infers roles, objects and permissions from the data structures (Aslam et al., 2020). These approaches all work in different perspectives and settings.

Another issue in current literature is that there is little emphasis on the role of data subjects (read: humans) in authorizing access to their own information. The work by Villata et al. (2013) allows users to manage who has access to their posts in the context of a Social Semantic Web; Pinto and Prazeres (2024) introduce the Fog of Things (FoT)-Personal Data Stores (PDS) paradigm where sensor data is stored in a Solid PDS under the control of the data subject, however their work is limited in scope.

The works described here are only concepts and experimental implementations with in some cases brief evaluation methods. Arshad et al. (2022) and Stojanov et al. (2018) evaluated their mechanisms based on self-defined principles for a semantic authorization model, Bader et al. (2021) performed an attack-vector analysis to assess the security against malicious actors, and Pinto and Prazeres (2024) briefly discuss how their concept holds up when compared against relevant articles of the GDPR. However, in order to most effectively evaluate a conceptual mechanism, one should implement and investigate it in a real-life situation to uncover unforeseen problems ¹

¹For an example of this, see van Reisen et al. (2021)

1.1 Synthesis

Governments consist of large dynamic distributed networks which create and control large volumes of data which has to be used for a large range of legal obligations. Proper authorization mechanisms can assist in ensuring data protection regulations are enforced in these processes, however research into their implementation is limited. This calls for an investigation into existing distributed authorization techniques, and the challenges with their implementation in real world scenarios.

2 Research Objectives

Main Research Objective: Implement and evaluate distributed, semantic and dynamic authorization mechanisms within a public administration.

- SRO1.** Create a mapping of the properties of existing distributed, semantic and dynamic authorization mechanisms.
- SRO2.** Define in which contexts these mechanisms are applicable, and delineate potential gaps.
- SRO3.** Assess the capacity that data subjects should have in exerting control over their sensitive information within different specific settings.
- SRO4.** Design and implement authorization mechanisms in different real-world settings within a public administration.
- SRO5.** Evaluate the implementation process and performance

3 Research Questions

Main Research Question: How can a semantic and dynamic authorization mechanism be implemented to automatically ensure compliance with data protection regulations in a public administration?

- SRQ1.** What are the state of the art distributed, semantic and dynamic authorization mechanisms in research and industry?
- SRQ2.** When are these existing authorization mechanisms applicable, and when should new methodology be developed?
- SRQ3.** What role, if any, can data subjects play in controlling protected data pertaining to them?
- SRQ4.** What are challenges in implementing distributed and semantic authorization mechanisms in specific settings within a public administration?
- SRQ5.** How can these challenges and lessons inform a broader implementation?

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